

A new spectrophotometric method for determination of amoxicillin using bromophenol blue

M. R. Keskar and R. M. Jugade*

Department of Chemistry, R. T. M. Nagpur University, University Campus, Amravati Road, Nagpur-440 033, Maharashtra, India

E-mail : ravinj2001@yahoo.co.in

Abstract : Simple and rapid spectrophotometric method has been developed for the determination of amoxicillin in bulk and pharmaceutical formulations. The method is based on formation of blue ion-pair complex between amoxicillin and bromophenol blue in dimethylsulphoxide-acetonitrile medium with λ_{max} of 590 nm. Different conditions affecting the reaction have been studied and optimised. The composition of the complex was found to be 2 : 1 (amoxicillin : bromophenol blue). Under optimum conditions, the limit of detection was found to be $0.05 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ with linear range extending from 0.5 to $20 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$. The Sandell's sensitivity was found to be $0.0219 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$. The method has been successfully applied for the determination of amoxicillin in pharmaceutical formulations.

Keywords : Amoxicillin, bromophenol blue, ion-pair complex.

Introduction

Amoxicillin, semi-synthetic drug belongs to a class of antibiotics called as Penicillins. It is shown to be effective against a wide range of infections caused by wide range of Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria in both human and animals. In the past decade, amoxycillin is being used to treat infections of the middle ear (otitis media), tonsilis (tonsillitis and tonsillopharyngitis), throat, larynx (laryngitis), pharynx (pharyngitis), bronchi (bronchitis), lungs (pneumonia), urinary tract (UTI), skin etc.¹⁻³. It is listed in British and Indian Pharmacopea^{4,5}. Bromophenol blue (BPB) is a sulphonphthalein dye commonly used as indicator and spectrophotometric reagent. Structures of amoxicillin and bromophenol blue are shown in Fig. 1. Various methods reported in the literature for the estimation of

Fig. 1. Structures of (a) amoxicillin, (b) bromophenol blue.

amoxicillin include HPLC⁶, potentiometry⁷, spectrofluorometry⁸, flow-injection⁹, thin layer chromatography¹⁰, voltammetry¹¹ etc.

Spectrophotometric methods based on charge transfer and ion-pair complex formation are the most convenient methods for drug analysis. These methods are based on the formation of coloured complex between drug and suitable reagent. Charge transfer complex is also called as electron donor-acceptor complex in which a fraction of electric charge is transferred between the molecular entities. In ion-pair complex formation, ions of opposite electric charge are produced in the solution due to the electron transfer. Reported spectrophotometric methods of amoxicillin include complex formation with chloranilic acid⁶, hematoxyline¹², Mo^V-thiocyanate¹³, Folin-Ciocalteu phenol reagent¹⁴, methylene blue¹⁵, iodine and wool fast blue¹⁶.

Spectrophotometric methods have an important advantage of low cost instrumentation as compared to other methods involving similar sensitivity. The proposed method is based on formation of ion-pair complex of amoxicillin with bromophenol blue. Bromophenol blue has been used for the first time for amoxicillin estimation with significantly low detection limit, high sensitivity and wider dynamic range.

Results and discussion

Selection of solvent :

Various solvents like methanol, ethanol, acetone, dichloromethane, dichloroethane, dimethylsulphoxide, chloroform and acetonitrile were studied for solubility, complex formation, to achieve maximum sensitivity and product stability. Acetonitrile for bromophenol blue and dimethylsulphoxide for

amoxicillin were found to be most suitable solvents.

Absorption spectra :

Solutions of amoxicillin and bromophenol blue were prepared in dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO) and acetonitrile respectively. Absorption spectra of these two solutions were recorded. These two solutions were mixed when amoxicillin was found to form blue coloured ion-pair complex with bromophenol blue having absorbance maxima 590 nm (Fig. 2). Under experimental conditions, the reagent as well as the drug showed negligible absorbance while the complex showed maximum absorbance at 590 nm. Hence, it was concluded that the studies for quantitative analysis could be carried out at this wavelength.

Fig. 2. Absorption spectra of (1) 3.7 mg mL⁻¹ amoxicillin, (2) 80 μM bromophenol blue and (3) complex.

Stoichiometric relationship and stability studies :

Composition of ion-pair complex was established by applying Job's method of continuous variation. Equimolar solutions of drug and reagent were mixed in various proportions and absorbance of each mixture was recorded. The results indicated that the complex was formed in the ratio of 2 : 1 (D : R) (Fig. 3). Mechanism of formation of such complex with composition (DH)⁺₂(R)²⁻ has been discussed by Gainza and Konyeaso¹⁷. From Job's method, the stability constant of complex was found to be log *K* = 5.95 indicating high thermodynamic stability. Also Gibb's free energy change of

Fig. 3. Continuous variation plots for the ion-pair complex of amoxicillin with bromophenol blue in DMSO-acetonitrile medium at 590 nm, (1) $6 \times 10^{-5} M$, (2) $8 \times 10^{-5} M$, (3) $1 \times 10^{-4} M$ amoxicillin.

complex formation was found to be -3.4177×10^4 showing spontaneity of process.

Effect of time :

Mixture of drug and reagent was prepared; the optimum reaction time was determined by recording the absorbance of the formed complex at different time intervals. It was found that the ion-pair complex was formed instantaneously at room temperature and was stable for about 40 minutes. Hence, all further studies were carried out immediately after mixing of the drug and reagent solutions.

Effect of reagent concentration :

The optimum reagent concentration was determined by adding various concentrations of bromophenol blue to the drug solution. The colour intensity was found to increase with addition of bromophenol blue up to a $16 \mu M$ and decreased thereafter (Fig. 4). However, at this concentration, the linear range was found to be narrow. In order to have wider linear range, bromophenol blue concentration of $20 \mu M$ was selected for the preparation of calibration graph.

Fig. 4. Effect of bromophenol blue concentration on absorbance for (1) 7 µg mL⁻¹ and (2) 15 µg mL⁻¹ amoxicillin.

Analytical parameters :

Calibration curve was plotted between absorbance and concentration of amoxicillin. A linear absorbance-concentration correlation was found to be 40 fold from 0.5 to 20 µg mL⁻¹ with correlation coefficient 0.9988. The molar absorptivity was found to be 1.6869×10^4 L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹. The 3σ detection limit was found to be 0.05 µg mL⁻¹ with Sandell's sensitivity of 0.0219 µg cm⁻². Under optimum conditions, various analytical parameters were obtained as presented in Table 1. The value of correlation coefficient indicates good linearity of the present method. High value of molar absorptivity and lower value of Sandell's sensitivity reflect high sensitivity of the method.

Recovery studies :

Recovery studies were carried out for amoxicillin using calibration curve at three different concentrations over the linear range. The recoveries were found to be in vicinity of 100% (Table 2).

Accuracy and precision :

Accuracy expresses the closeness between the reference value and the found value. It was evaluated as percentage relative error between the measured concentrations and taken concentrations of amoxicillin. The precision of the method was calculated in terms of intermediate precision

Table 1. Collective data for the qualitative and statistical parameters using proposed method

Parameter	Findings
Solvent	DMSO–Acetonitrile (1 : 1)
λ_{\max} (nm)	590
Molar ratio (D : R)	2 : 1
Linear range ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$)	0.5–20
Slope	0.0455
Intercept	-0.0323
Linear regression equation	$A = 0.0455C - 0.0323$
Sandell's sensitivity ($\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$)	0.0219
Correlation coefficient (r)	0.9988
Coefficient of determination (r^2)	0.9976
Stability constant (log K)	5.95
Molar absorptivity ($\text{L mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$)	1.6869×10^4
LOD ^a ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$)	0.05
LOQ ^b ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$)	0.17
%RSD ^c (at 2 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$)	1.02
$\Delta G^{\circ d}$ (kJ mol^{-1})	-3.4177×10^4

^aLimit of detection. ^bLimit of Quantification. ^cRelative standard deviation. ^dFree energy change. A = Absorbance, C = Concentration of drug ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$).

Table 2. Recovery studies of amoxicillin

Sr. No.	Sample	Method	Taken ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$)	Found	Recovery ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) ^a	Mean \pm SD (%)
			7.5	7.4	98.66	
1.	Amoxicillin	BPB	12.5	12.6	100.80	100.01 \pm 1.17
			17.5	17.6	100.57	

^aAverage of three determinations.

(intra-day and inter-day). Three different concentrations of amoxicillin were analysed in three replicates during same day (intra-day precision) and three consecutive days (inter-day precision). RSD (%) values of intra-day and inter-day studies show good precision (Table 3).

Application :

The proposed method was applied to the determination of amoxicillin in pharmaceutical formulations as tablets, capsules and oral suspension. Five tablets or capsules were weighed and average weight of one tablet or one

Table 3. Evaluation of inter-day and intra-day precision and accuracy

Sample	Taken ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Inter-day (n = 3)			Intra-day (n = 3)		
		Found ^a	%RSD ^b	% RE ^c	Found ^a ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	%RSD ^b	% RE ^c
Amoxicillin	7.5	7.4	0.38	1.33	7.6	0.33	1.33
	12.5	12.6	0.28	0.80	12.6	0.46	0.80
	17.5	17.6	0.27	0.57	17.8	0.27	1.71

^aAverage of three determinations. ^b% Relative standard deviation. ^c% Relative error.

capsule was determined. They were powdered and about 0.05 g was exactly weighed and shaken with 30 ml dimethylsulphoxide for 30 min. It was filtered with Watmann filter paper no. 40 and made up 50 ml with dimethylsulphoxide. The same procedure was applied for oral suspension of drug using 1 ml suspension. Suitable aliquots were analysed using optimized procedure. The antibiotic content of tablet, capsule and oral suspension were calculated from calibration curve and also by standard addition method. The results were found to be in agreement with the reported values (Table 4).

Table 4. Analysis of pharmaceutical formulations by calibration curve and standard addition method

Sr. No.	Pharmaceutical preparations ^a	Labelled amount (mg)	Found amount ^b (mg)	
			Calibration curve method	Standard addition method ^b
1.	Rexel capsules	250	250.60 \pm 3.99	243.80 \pm 0.03
2.	Rexel capsules	500	510.63 \pm 7.55	498.93 \pm 0.65
3.	Moxkid tablets	125	124.96 \pm 2.30	126.06 \pm 1.01
4.	Novamax liquid	125	126.36 \pm 1.26	122.50 \pm 1.21

^aRanbaxy laboratories products. ^b(Average \pm SD) of three observations.

Conclusion

The developed method was found to be versatile and has many advantages over the previously reported methods. A comparison of this method with reported methods has been presented in Table 5. It has been observed that, this method has wider linear dynamic range, higher molar absorptivity, higher Sandell's sensitivity and low detection limit as compared to

Table 5. Comparison of various spectrophotometric methods

Reagent used	Linear range ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	LOD ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Molar absorptivity ($\text{L mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$)	Sandell's sensitivity ($\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$)	Applications	Ref.
Chloranilic acid	10–200	1.5	1.3×10^3	0.2741	Tablet, injections	6
Hematoxyline	20–80	–	–	–	Tablet, capsules, urine	12
Mo ^V -thiocyanate	7.5–15	0.75	5.28×10^3	0.073	Capsules	13
Folin-Ciocalteu phenol	10–34	0.01	1.17×10^4	–	Capsules	14
Methylene blue	3.5–85	3.0	6.0×10^3	0.008	Capsule, injection, syrup	15
Iodine and wool fast blue	0.8–4	–	4.85×10^4	0.00864	Tablets, capsules, injection	16
Bromophenol blue	0.5–20	0.05	1.6869×10^4	0.0219	Capsule, tablet, syrup	Present work

most of the reported methods. The method consists of a single step reaction with no extraction process and so simpler compared to reported methods^{13,15}.

This method requires only dye and solvents which are comparatively cheaper and readily available. The method is simple as it does not involve adjustment of critical conditions like temperature, pH or tedious sample preparation. This method has many advantages over other analytical methods due to its simplicity, sensitivity, rapidity, low cost instrumentation and accuracy. Due to these advantages, this method can be used for quality control and routine analysis of amoxicillin.

Experimental

Spectrophotometric studies were carried out with Spectronic 20D+ (Thermo-Spectronic) visible spectrophotometer. A Mettler H-51AR balance (Ner-Parma instrument Corp. L.C. = 0.01 mg) was used for weighing purpose. All chemicals and reagents used were of analytical grade. Amoxicillin was kindly provided by ZIM laboratories. Bromophenol blue,

HPLC grade acetonitrile, dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO) were obtained from LOBA Chemie.

Stock solution of amoxicillin was prepared as 0.01 M in dimethyl sulphoxide. 0.01 M bromophenol blue in acetonitrile was used as a stock solution. The solutions were further diluted as per requirement.

Suitable aliquots of amoxicillin solution were transferred into volumetric flasks. To it, 2.5 ml of 8×10^{-5} M bromophenol blue solution was added and volume was made up to 10 ml with 1 : 1 dimethylsulphoxide-acetonitrile mixture. This made the final concentration of bromophenol blue to 20 μ M. The absorbance of blue coloured solution was measured at 590 nm against appropriate reagent blank.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to UGC, New Delhi for financial assistance under Start-up-Grant.

References

1. R. N. Brogden, R. C. Heel, T. M. Speight and G. S. Avery, *Drugs*, 1979, **18**, 184.
2. W. S. Lim, S. Gander, R. G. Finch and J. T. Mactarlane, *J. Antimicrob. Chemotherapy*, 2007, **46**, 835.
3. S. P. Kaur, R. Rao and S. Nanda, *Int. J. Pharm. Pharm. Sci.*, 2011, **3**, 30.
4. British Pharmacopoeia Commission, Vol. I & Vol. II, London, 2009.
5. Indian Pharmacopoeia Commission, 5th ed., Vol. II, Ghaziabad, India, 2007.
6. K. Basavaiah, K. Thappa, N. R. Prasad, S. G. Hirivanna and K. B. Vinay, *Indian J. Chem. Tech.*, 2009, **16**, 265.
7. M. M. Shoukry, *Talanta*, 1992, **39**, 1625.
8. A. F. El Waily, A. A. Gazy and S. F. Belal, *J. Pharma. Biomed. Anal.*, 1999, **20**, 643.
9. Y. Li, Y. Tang, H. Yao and J. Fu, *Luminiscence*, 2003, **18**, 313.
10. G. Indrayanto, T. K. Sa and S. Widjaja, *J. AOAC Int.*, 2000, **83**, 1493.
11. M. Fouladge, M. R. Hadjmohammadi, M. A. Khalilzadeh, P. Biparra, N. Teymoori and H. Beitollah, *Int. J. Electrochem. Sci.*, 2011, **6**, 1355.

Keskar & Jugade

12. G. P. A. Raghavendra and R. V. Suryanarayana, *J. Pharm. Res.*, 2010, **3**, 869.
13. G. G. Mohamed, *J. Pharm. Biomed. Anal.*, 2001, **24**, 561.
14. A. D. Ahmad, N. Rahman and F. Islam, *J. Anal. Chem.*, 2004, **59**, 119.
15. B. B. Prasad and S. Gupta, *Indian J. Pharm. Sci.*, 2000, **62**, 261.
16. C. S. Sastry, S. G. Rao, Y. P. Naidu and K. R. Srinivas, *Talanta*, 1998, **45**, 1227.
17. A. H. Gainza and R. I. Konyeaso, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1991, **69**, 937.